

ANALYZING THE MOBILITY CUSTOMS OF THE URBAN POPULATION USING MOBILE NETWORK DATA

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INTRODUCTION

*A city is more than a place in space, it is a drama in time. –
Patrick Geddes*

RESEARCH GOALS

- Develop methodologies to characterize the mobility patterns of the urban population quantitatively
- Implement a data processing framework for calculating the mobility indicators
 - e.g., home and work locations, Entropy, Radius of Gyration
- Enrich mobile network data with other data sources to characterize the socioeconomic status (SES)
- Design a method to analyze the relationship between the mobility and SES

CALL DETAIL RECORDS

- billed activity (calls, short messages, data transfer)
- *who*, when, where
 - *anonymized*
- additional information
 - gender, age, subscription type, type allocation code (TAC)
 - cell-map for geographical positioning

POSITIONING

overlapping cells

APRIL 2017 DATA SET

- Vodafone Hungary (market share: 25.5%[1])
- 955,035,169 records
- 1,629,275 unique SIM cards

THESIS 1: NEW METHOD FOR EVALUATION OF THE COMMUTING BASED ON MOBILE NETWORK DATA

I have designed a method to describe the commuting patterns of the population quantitatively. The method is based on the statistical detection of the home and work locations using anonymized mobile network data. I have validated the results by comparing them to census-based commuting analyses and found good agreement between the determined mobility patterns and census-based data.

HOME AND WORK LOCATIONS – METHODOLOGY

Home

- the most frequent cell where a SIM card is present
- during the evenings and the nights on workdays
- from 22:00 to 06:00
- and all day on holidays

Workplace

- the most frequent cell where a SIM card is present
- during working hours on workdays
- between 09:00 and 16:00

HOME AND WORK LOCATIONS – HEATMAP

home activity

HOME AND WORK LOCATIONS – HEATMAP

home activity

workplace activity

POPULATION

KSH (2017)[2]

CDR (April 2017)

POPULATION – CORRELATION

Pearson's R is 0.9213

COMMUTING TO BUDAPEST

From Dunakeszi, census [3]

COMMUTING TO BUDAPEST

From Dunakeszi, census [3]; Pearson's $R=0.9416$ (CDR vs. 2011)

COMMUTING BY AGE GROUPS

Microcensus (2016)[4]

CDR (April 2017)

Pearson's R = 0.8977

THESIS 2: CORRELATION BETWEEN HOME AND WORKPLACE PRICE-LEVELS

Using anonymous mobile network data, I have demonstrated that people living in a less expensive neighborhood usually work in a less expensive area, based on housing prices of the home and the work locations. It has also been presented that people, who live in a more expensive neighborhood, tend to work in a more expensive area.

CORRELATION BETWEEN HOME AND WORKPLACE PRICE-LEVEL

THESIS 3: NEW INDICATORS FOR CHARACTERIZING MOBILITY CUSTOMS

I have introduced new indicators for quantitative evaluation of wake-up time and bedtime in an urban environment. The wake-up and bedtime conditions were determined by the rate of mobile network activity in the morning and evening hours.

Two subscriber aggregation methods (area and inhabitant-based) have been developed to determine the wake-up characteristics of a geographical area or a group of subscribers.

AGGREGATION METHODS

Area based

AGGREGATION METHODS

Area based

Inhabitant based

CALCULATION OF THE WAKE-UP AND THE BEDTIMES

CALCULATION OF THE WAKE-UP AND THE BEDTIMES

LATER BEDTIME ON LONGER DAYS

April 2017

June 2016

WHEN DO THE MALLS OPEN?

Example of the area-based approach

THESIS 4: NEW METHOD TO ANALYZE THE CORRELATION OF MOBILITY AND SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS

I have designed a method using Principal Component Analysis to evaluate socioeconomic status depending on the indicators of human mobility. Housing prices have been used to characterize the socioeconomic status of the population. I have found differences in the mobility customs within the different socioeconomic classes, so that the socioeconomic status can be inferred from the mobility.

INPUT OF PCA

HomePr	WorkPr	GYR_WD_0.5	GYR_WD_1.0	...	GYR_WD_20	ENT_WD_0.05	...	ENT_WD_0.95
0.2	min-Q1	0.421	0.579	...	0.000	0.000	...	0.045
0.3		0.489	0.632	...	0.000	0.000	...	0.054
...	
1.1		0.100	0.200	...	0.000	0.000	...	0.147
0.2	Q1-Q3	0.287	0.401	...	0.012	0.000	...	0.135
...	
1.1		0.324	0.588	...	0.000	0.026	...	0.105
0.2	Q3-max	0.051	0.092	...	0.000	0.008	...	0.121
...	
1.1		0.625	0.813	...	0.000	0.182	...	0.091

SCATTER PLOT OF THE 2-COMPONENT PCA

Marker size indicates the home price category, the type denotes work price category, and the color refers to Weekdays or Weekends.

THESIS 5: INTRODUCTION OF CELLPHONE PRICE AS SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS INDICATOR

I have fused cellphone prices and release dates with the mobile network data to analyze the mobility customs in contrast to the price and the age of the subscribers' cellphone. I found that the cellphone price and age are eligible to characterize a subscriber's socioeconomic status.

SCATTER PLOT OF THE 2-COMPONENT PCA

Marker size indicates subscriber age category, the color represents the phone price category, and the workdays and holidays are distinguished by the marker type.

THESIS 6: THE RELATION OF WAKE-UP TIME AND SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS

I demonstrated a relationship between the wake-up time and the mobility customs, as well as the socioeconomic status. The subscribers living in less expensive apartments get up earlier than those who live in pricier neighborhoods. The same tendency holds regarding mobile phone prices: subscribers who own more expensive cellphones tend to get up later.

WAKE-UP TIME VS. MOBILITY

Wake-up Time in contrast of the normalized daily Entropy

Wake-up Time in contrast of the normalized daily Radius of Gyration

WAKE-UP TIME VS. SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS

Wake-up time distribution
by housing price

Wake-up time distribution
by phone price

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THANK YOU FOR THE ATTENTION!

